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Kasuwanci a Duniyar Intanet: Kalubalen Hausawan Karni na 21

Na

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Tsakure

Sannu a hankali al'ummun duniya na kara rungumar kasuwancin duniyar intanet. Ciki har da Hausawa. Wannan ne babban dalilin gudanar da binciken inda aka nazarci nau'uka da yanayen-yanayen kasuwancin kan intanet da alfanu da kalubalen da ke tare da su da kuma hanyoyin fuskantar wadannan kalubale. Manyan dabarun da aka yi amfani da su wajen tattaraa bayanai su ne nazartar bayanai kan intanet kai tsaye da kuma hira da Hausawan da abin ya shafa. An dora aikin a kan ra'in Pulatoriyya (Platonism) inda aka kalli kasuwancin duniyar intanet a matsayin mai cin gashin kansa daga kasuwancin duniyar zahiri (duk da cudanyar da suke yi da juna a wadansu lokuta). Binciken ya gano nau'ukan kasuwancin intanet guda biyar da Hausawa ke gudanarwa. A bangare guda kuwa, binciken ya gano cewa, kasuwancin kan intanet ya kasance cigaba duk da wadansu kalubale da ya kunsu. Daga karshe binciken ya ba da shawarwari da suka hada da sa hannun gwamnatoji da hukumomi da daidai mutane domin bin mata kai da amfani da dabarun kauce wa gurbata muhalli da yanayi yayin gudanar da hada-hadar kasuwanci a duniyar intanet.

Fitulun Kalmomi: Kasuwanci; Intanet; Pulatoriyya

1.0 Gabatarwa

Kamar yadda duniya ba a wuri guda take tsaye ba,¹ haka ma al'amuran da ke cikinta kullum na kan sauyawa. Wadannan sauye-sauye sun shafi dukkannin bangarorin rayuwa da wanzuwar dukkannin halittu.² A bangarori da dama na rayuwa, sababbin abubuwa da zamani ke zuwa da su na kasancewa hanjin jimina, wato akwai na ci sannan akwai na zubarwa. Hakan ne kuma ya sa yake da matuƙar muhimmanci da a rika nazartar sababbin abubuwan da zamani ya samar. Wannan zai ba da damar cin gajiyar alfanin da ke tattare da sauye-sauyen tare da samar da nagartattun matakan fuskantar kalubalen da ke tattare da su.

Fannin kasuwancin Hausawa babban bagire ne da har kullum ke sanya rigar zamaninsa. Karni na ashirin da ɗaya (K21) ya zo da sauyi na musamman a wannan fannin. A karnin ne aka samu bunkasar intanet. Sannu a hankali intanet ya mamaye bangarorin rayuwa, ciki har da lamarin kasuwanci. Sannu a hankali har aka kai bagiren da a yau kasuwanci ba ya bunkasa ya kai matakin koli har sai ya rungumi duniyar intanet.

Hausawan wannan zamani ba a bar su a baya ba wajen tsunduma harkar kasuwanci da ke da alaƙa da duniyar intanet. Wannan kuwa ya kasance cikin salailai daban-daban, tun daga kan dillanci, talla, har zuwa nau'ukan ayyukan da ke bukatar fwarewa da ilimummukan fannoni na musamman. Bisa wannan, akwai bukatar gudanar da bincike domin nazartar yanaye-yanayen kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Kai tsaye wannan takarda ta mayar da hankali kan (i) nazartar nau'uka da fasalce-fasalcen kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet, (ii) kalubale da alfanun da ke tattare da kasuwancin, da kuma (iii) matakan fuskantar kalubalen tare da inganta harkallolin.

¹ Ilimin kimiyya da addini da al'ada duk sun tabbatar da cewa duniya na kan juyawa cikin wadansu nau'uka da salailan tafiya da kowanne ke da tasiri ko sakamako da yake samarwa. Domin karin bayani, ana iya duba Hukumar Binciken Tarihi Da Al'adu Ta Jihar Katsina da 'Yar Kyaure, (n.d.) ko Na, (2013).

² Babu wata halitta da lokaci ba ya tasiri a kanta. Nau'ukan tasirin da ake iya samu na iya kasancewa wadanda halittun ke da iko a kansu (misali kirkire-kirkire da fere-fere), ko wadanda ba su da iko a kansu (misali raguwar girman jikin 'yan'adam da raguwar yawan shekaru da suke yi a duniya).

1.1 Dabarun gudanar da bincike

Kadadar wannan bincike ta takaita ne ga kasuwanci da ke da alaka da intanet. An sake takaita kadadar ga kasuwancin Hausawa. Ba a iyakance waɗansu kafafe da za a mayar da hankali a kansu ba. Dalili kuwa shi ne, binciken ya kudiri aniyar waiwaitar duk nau'ukan hada-hadar kasuwancin kan intanet da ake damawa da Hausawa.

An tattara bayanan majiyar farko (primary source) ta hanyoyi guda biyu. Hanya ta farko ita ce binciken kai tsaye a kafafen intanet da ake gudanar da hada-hadar kasuwanci. Hanya ta biyun kuwa ita ce hira da Hausawa da ke gudanar da sana'o'i masu alaka da intanet domin samun bayanai daga tushe. An bi dabarun tantance bayanan da aka samu daga tattaunawar ta hanyar maimaita tattaunawa da waɗansu mutane na daban da kuma ta hanyar tabbatar da bayanai daga kididdigar alkaluma da ke wallafe a kafafen intanet.

Wuraren da aka tattara bayanai da ke matakin majiya ta biyu (secondary data) sun haɗa da littattafai da mujallu da mukalu da kuma bidiyoyi da hotuna da rubuce-rubucen da ke kafafen intanet daban-daban. Duk waɗannan sun taimaka wajen share hanya da karin haske tare da yin jagoranci wajen fayyace muhamman batutuwa da suka shafi binciken.

1.2 Ra'in bincike

An dora wannan bincike a kan ra'in Pulatoriyya (Platonism).³ Kamar yadda Gerson, (2005: 253) ya bayyana, wannan ra'i ne da ya ginu kan fahimta da falsafofin Plato,⁴ duk kuwa da cewa yakan samu sauye-sauye daga lokaci zuwa lokaci. Ra'in na iƙirarin cewa, duniya tamkar kashi biyu take; duniyar zahiri (bayyananniyar duniya) da kuma ta baɗini (boyayyiyar duniya). Lamura na gudana a waɗannan duniyoyi sannan suna iya cuɗanya da juna. Haka kuma, al'amuran da ake gudanarwa a ɗaya daga cikin duniyoyin na iya shafar ɗayar.

³ Domin karin bayani kan wannan ra'i ana iya duba Gerson, (2005: 253); Gerson, (2013); Thein, (2018); da Sani, (2022).

⁴ Plato ya kasance ɗaya daga cikin fitattun masana falsafa da suka rayu farnuka huɗu zuwa biyar kafin zuwan Annabi Isa. Domin samun cikakken bayani kan tarihinsa da ayyukansa, ana iya duba Meinwald, (2020).

A bisa wannan ra'in, takardar na da hasashen cewa, akwai nau'ukan kasuwancin da ake gudanarwa a duniyar intanet ta sigogi makamantan yadda ake gudanar da su a duniyar zahiri. Haka kuma, kasuwancin da aka fara a duniyar zahiri na iya komawa duniyar badini (intanet). Ana kuma iya dauko kasuwanci daga duniyar badini a dawo da shi duniyar zahiri.

Ra'in Pulatoriyya ya yi jagoranci a binciken ta fuskar fito da nau'in alaka da ke tsakanin kasuwancin duniyar zahiri da duniyar intanet. Ya kuma nuna wuraren da bangarorin biyu ke cin gashin kansu da kuma wuraren da suke cudanya da juna cikin salon shigar giza-gizai. Bugu da kari, ra'in ya taimaka wajen kwankwancewa da kalailaice bayanar da binciken ya tattara.

2.1 Taliyon kalmar "kasuwanci" a kadadar al'adun Hausawa

"Kasuwanci" da "sana'a" kalmomi ne masu tafiya kafada da kafada. Duk da alakar da ke tsakanin kalmomin biyu, akwai marubuta da suka yi kokarin ba da ma'anar *sana'a* da ta *kasuwanci* a kebance. Rumbun Ilimi (n.d.) ya bayyana cewa Hausawa na sana'a tun wajajen shekarar 1349, inda kuma ya ce sana'a: "kalma ce da aka aro ta daga Larabci, kuma take daukar ma'ana ta samar da wani abin amfani ta hanyar hikima a Hausance." Ya dauki kasuwanci abu mai cin gashin kansa a matsayin hanyar saye da sayarwa. Wannan ra'ayi ya yi daidai da na Buhari, (2021: 1)¹ inda yake cewa:

Kasuwanci dai yana nufin saye da sayarwa na wani abu ko kuma haja wanda abun nan yana iya kasancewa wanda ake gani ne kuma wanda ba a gani⁵ ne kamar mutum ya yi wani aiki a biya shi to duka suna daukar ma'anar kasuwanci. Buhari, (2021: 1)¹

A fahimtar wannan takarda, tattauna *kasuwanci* a kadadar al'adun Hausawa ba zai kammala ba har sai an hada shi da *sana'o'in Hausawa*. Hasali ma a bagire da dama suna iya wakiltar juna. Muhammad, (2020: 224) ya bayyana ma'anar sana'a a matsayin "hanyoyin da ake gudanar da saye da sayarwa." Kai tsaye za a iya cewa wannan ma'ana

⁵ Lallai wannan ma'ana ta kasuwanci da Buhari (2021) ta fara fito da iƙirarin Pulatoriyya ta cewar gaskiya nau'i biyu ce, wato wacce ake gani da wacce ba a gani. Ma'anar ta Buhari ta fara tabbatar da hakan kamar yadda ya bayyana daga cikin kasuwanci akwai waɗanda ba a ganin su.

tana bayani ne a kan *kasuwanci*. Ta yiwu cudɓɓeniyar da ke tsakanin *sana'a* da *kasuwanci* ne ya ja hankalin Muhammad wajen ba da wannan ma'ana.

Ko Rumbun Ilimi, (2020: 1) da Buhari, (2021: 1)¹ da Buhari, (2021: 1)² da suka rarrabe tsakanin *kasuwanci* da *sana'a*, akwai wuraren da bayanansu ke nuna ba a iya rabe su. Misali, Buhari ya kawo “noma” da “kiwo” da “ɗinki” a cikin misalan kasuwanci. Ya yi hakan ne a fokarin nuna yadda Hausawa ke samun kuɗi da su.

Idan har sai an kalailaice bambancin da ke tsakanin *sana'a* da *kasuwanci*, to ana iya cewa *sana'a* ita ce hanyar amfani da fasaha da hikima da kuma kayan aiki domin sarrafa wani abin amfani da za a iya sayarwa ko a musanya da wani abu mai daraja. Kasuwanci kuwa fasaha ce ta saye da sayarwa ko musanyen abubuwa masu daraja domin samun riba. Ko ba komai, za a tarar da cewa duk *sana'a* da za a gudanar (kamar kira, saka, wanzanci da sauransu) to sai kasuwanci ya shiga ciki (ciniki, talla, da sauransu). Haka kuma duk kasuwancin da za a gudanar, to ana yi ne ta amfani da kayayyakin da an same su ne sakamakon *sana'o'i*.

2.2 Kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar zamani

Cudɓanyar Hausawa da bakin al'ummu musamman Larabawa da Turawa da kuma sauyawan zamani sun samar da sauye-sauye da dama a fannin kasuwancin Hausawa.⁶ Haka kuma, a har kullum Hausawa na fara samun wayewa ta fuskar kasuwanci tare da faɗaɗawa da bunkasa *sana'o'insu*. Bunkasar kasuwancin Hausawa na kasancewa cikin manyan sigogi guda biyu kamar haka:

1. **Bunkasar kasuwanci:** Bunkasar kasuwanci na faruwa ne yayin da ribar da ɗan kasuwa ke samu a cikin wani ayyanannen lokaci (misali wata guda) ta faru.

⁶ Wannan takarda na da ra'ayin cewa, ko da Hausawa ba su yi cudɓanya da kowace al'umma ba, za su samu sauye-sauye da cigaban zamani a harkokin rayuwarsu. A har kullum halin rayuwa na tilasta wa ɗan'adam amfani da fikira wajen sama wa kansa sauki da mafita daga kalubalen da ke dabaibaiye da matakan rayuwarsa. Saboda haka, yadda kullum yanayin duniya ke sauyawa tare da bullo da sababbin kalubale da ɗan'adam bai taɓa cin karo da su ba, haka shi ɗan'adam ke fara kirkiro hanyoyin fiskantar matsalolin. Waɗannan su ke haɗuwa su samar da cigaban zamani. Cropley, (2019) ya kawo cikakken bayani kan wannan falsafa.

Wannan na iya kasancewa sakamakon ɗaya daga cikin abubuwan da aka zayyano a kasa:

- a. Fadadar kasuwanci
- b. Daukakuwar darajar kasuwanci
- c. Raguwar kudaden da ake kashewa kan sana'a⁷

2. **Fadadar kasuwanci:** Kasuwanci na samun fadada ne yayin da kayayyakin da yake samarwa ke isa hannun adadin mutane sama da yadda abin yake a baya. Wannan ma na iya kasancewa ta fuskokin da suka hada da:

- a. Fadadar kasuwanci na cikin gida⁸
- b. Fadadar kasuwanci na waje⁹

Dukkannin matakan biyu (bunkasa da fadadar kasuwanci) na samuwa sakamakon tasirin zamani. Dalilan samuwarsu sun hada da (i) saukafar hanyoyin sufuri da (ii) bunkasar hanyoyin sadarwa da (iii) sababbin matakan sarrafawa da makamantansu.

Ana iya kallon tasirin zamani kan kasuwancin Hausawa ta fuskoki daban-daban kamar haka:

- i. Kare-Kare
- ii. Kirfire-Kirfire
- iii. Huldaiyya

Kamar yadda masu iya magana ke cewa "ruwa ba ya tsami banza," akwai dalilai daban-daban da ke samar da waɗannan sauye-sauye a sha'anin kasuwancin Hausawa. Idan aka ce "tasirin zamani," dunksulallen zance ne da ke tattare da abubuwa mabambanta. Yayin da aka fasa cikinsa, za a tarar da daiɗaikun sabubban da suka hada da:

⁷ Ana iya samun raguwar kudaden da ake kashewa wurin gudanar da sana'a ta hanyoyin da suka hada samun kayayyakin sana'a mafiya sauki ko samun saukafan hanyoyin jigilar kayayyakin sana'a zuwa wurin sarrafa su, da dai makamantansu.

⁸ Wannan na faruwa yayin da aka samu farin mutane a muhalli ko mafwabta ko cikin al'ummar mai sana da suka fara amfani da kayayyakin da mai sana'ar ke samarwa.

⁹ Wannan na faruwa yayin da waɗansu al'ummu na nesa suka fara amfani da kayayyakin da mai sana'a ke samarwa.

- a. **Daukar hannu:** Wannan ya shafi kwaikwayo daga fasahohin waɗansu al'ummu na daban. Misali, a yau maƙeran Hausawa na samar da kayayyaki daban-daban ta hanyar ɗaukar hannu daga kere-kere ƙasashen ketare. Haka ma kafintoci Hausawa ke kera abubuwa ta hanyar ɗaukar hannu. Babban misali shi ne bodin babbar mota (roka) da ake amfani da kataki da ƙarafa wajen ƙerawa.
- b. **Yanayi/Tilasci:** Sauyin yanayi da ya shafi rayuwa ko muhalli na kai ga an samar da sababbin kasuwanci tare da sauye-sauye a waɗanda ake da su. Kasuwancin sayar da datar intanet da ta POS da Hausawa suka runguma a yau, duk misalai ne na sababbin nau'ukan kasuwanci da suka samu a sakamakon tasirin yanayi. Haka kuma awara/wara/kwai-da-kwai da ke ƙara mamaye ƙasar Hausa na da alaƙa da yanayin yunwa da talauci da Hausawa ke ciki. A lokacin annobar korona kuwa (2019-2022), Hausawa da dama sun tara kuɗi ta hanyar kasuwancin takunkumin fuska (face mask).
- c. **Yayi:** Akan samu lokutan da yayi ne kawai ke sauyawa. Sannu a hankali sai a saki wani abu da aka yi riƙo da shi a koma wani daban. Irin wannan sauyi na kasance cikin yanayin da abu ne mai wuya a iya bayanin mene ne haƙifanin dalilin da ya sa aka saki al'adar baya. Sau da dama sai dai a ce “wayewa.”¹⁰

3.0 Kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet

A wannan bagire, kasuwanci na nufin duk wani abin da za a yi domin samun kuɗi ko wani abu mai darajar da zai iya wakiltar kuɗi ko wanda za a iya musanya shi da kuɗi. Wannan ya kasance sabanin duk waɗansu ra'ayoyi da ke ɗaukar “sana'a” da “kasuwanci” a matayin nau'ukan haƙƙalloli guda biyu masu cin gashin kansu. Takardar ta tsaya kan wannan ra'ayi ne kasancewar haƙƙallolin biyu na da alaƙa da juna ta yadda

¹⁰ Babban misalin wannan shi ne yadda matasan Hausawa suka riƙi babban wando (fantalo) a matsayin kwalliya (tsukakken wando kuma ya kasance ƙauyanci), har zuwa wajajen shekarar 2008. Daga baya kuma sai yayi ya sauya inda aka ɗauki fantalo a matsayin ƙauyanci, shi kuwa tsukakken wando ya koma wayewa. Duk lokacin da irin haka ya faru, masu kasuwancin wandunan dole su sauya domin samar da abubuwan da mutane za su saya ba waɗanda za su yi kwantai ba.

ba za su iya cin gashin kansu ko ware kansu daga juna ba musamman a bagiren duniyar intanet.

Sani, Buba da Mohammad (2019 p. 48) sun rawaito Poon da Swatman na cewa: “Amfani da intanet a tsakanin masu kananan sana'o'i ya zama wani fitaccen lamari (batu) ga manazarta a fannin ilimin kimiyyar intanet da na kasuwanci.” Duniyar intanet shakundum ce ta fuskar tattara kasuwanci daban-daban. Mafi yawan motsi/lamura da ke kan intanet kasuwanci ne. Kusan komai da ke kan intanet na da darajar da za a iya sarrafa shi domin samun kuɗi – wato dai za a iya gudanar da kasuwanci da shi. A intanet akan samu har tsafaffin sana’o’in Hausawa da aka fara mantawa da su. Sannan akan iya yin kasuwanci da waɗannan tsafaffin sana’o’i ta hanyoyi daban-daban, kamar sayar da bayanan, sayar da hotuna da bidiyoyin, ko dōra tallace-tallace a kafafen da suke.

Wannan ɓangare na takardar zai tattauna lamarin kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet karkashin muhimman kanu guda uku, wato nau’o’in kasuwancin da nasarorinsu da kuma kalubalen da suke fuskanta.

3.1 Nau’o’in kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet

Tuni Hausawa da dama suka tsunduma cikin hada-hadar kasuwanci da suka shafi duniyar intanet. Nau’ukan kasuwancin kan intanet da ake samun Hausawa ciki na da matuƙar yawa. Duk da haka, ana iya bayanin su cikin manyan rukunoni guda biyar kamar haka:

1. Firilancin na Kan Intanet (Online Freelancing)
2. Baje Haja/Koli
3. Dillanci
4. Kasuwancin Kudin Intanet
5. Talla (Advertisement)

3.1.1 Firilancin na kan intanet (Online freelancing)¹¹

Aikin wucin gadi na kan intanet ya shafi duk wani nau'in aiki da ke buƙatar wata ƙwarewa ta musamman domin gundunar da ita. Manyan hajojin da masu ire-iren waɗannan kasuwanci ke kasawa su ne basirarsu da ƙwarewarsu.¹² A wannan fannin, boyayyiyar gaskiya ba ta takaita ga kasa hajar baɗini ba. A maimakon haka, farfajiyar kasuwancin ma ta baɗini ce, wato duniyar intanet. Daya daga cikin alfanun irin wannan aiki shi ne kamar yadda Downey, (2022 p. 1) ke cewa:

A freelancer is not an employee of a firm and may therefore be at liberty to complete different jobs concurrently by various individuals or firms...

Fassara:

Firilanca ba ma'aikaci ne da wata ma'aikata ta ɗauka aikin dindindin ba, don haka yana da damar gudanarwa da kammala ayyuka daban-daban a lokaci guda, waɗanda yake karɓa daga mutane ko ma'aikatu daban-daban...

Daga cikin ire-iren sana' o'in akwai:

1. Firilancin da suka shafi kimiyyar harshe (language and linguistic services)

Ma'aikatan firilancin karkashin kimiyyar harshe na gudanar da ayyuka da suka haɗa da:

- a. Bin ƙwaƙƙwafin ma'ana (linguistic evaluation)
- b. Fassara (translation)
- c. Fassara da ƙirƙira (transcreation)
- d. Karatun bita (proofreading)
- e. Ƙirƙirar rubutu (content writing)
- f. Subtitling (fassarar kan sikirin)
- g. Tafintanci (interpretation)
- h. Tsara rubutu (typesetting)

¹¹ Kasancewar wannan takarda ba ta ci kawo da wata amintacciyar fassara ta "online freelancing" ba, an baddala ta zuwa "firilancin na kan intanet."

¹² Waɗannan hajoji na daga cikin misalan boyayyun gaskiya da ra'in Pulatoriyya ke magana a kansu.

- i. Maye sauti (voice over)

2. Firilansin da suka shafi intanet da na'urori

Ma'aikatan firilancin karkashin intanet da na'urori na gudanar da ayyuka da suka hada da:

- a. Ba da tsaro ga kafafen intanet da na'urori (cyber security)
- b. Gina kafafen intanet (website design)
- c. Gina manhajoji (software programming)
- d. Gwada inganci da amincin manhajoji da kafafen intanet (beta testing)
- e. Gwada kutse (penetration testing)

3. Firilancin da suka shafi gyaran hotuna da bidiyoyi

Ma'aikatan firilancin karkashin gyara hotuna da bidiyoyi na gudanar da ayyuka da suka hada da:

- a. Gyara hotuna da bidiyoyi (photo and video editing)
- b. Tsara hotuna da zane-zane (graphic design and illustration)

4. Firilancin da suka shafi bincike

Masu firilancin da ke karkashin rukunin bincike na gudanar da ayyuka da suka hada da:

- a. Kalailaice bayanai (data analysis)
- b. Neman bayanai (data sourcing)

Ko bayan wadannan akwai wadansu masu tarin yawa da suka hada da: Jami'in talla (Marketing agent) da watsa labarai (media) da aiki a matsayin kwararren jami'i mai ba da shawarwari da suka shafi kudade (finance expert) ko shawarwari da suka shafi doka (legal expert) ko mai jigila (gig work) da dai makamantansu. Da yawa daga cikin wadannan nau'ukan sana'o'i akan same su a duniyar zahiri. Sai dai na duniyar zahirin sun yi karanci sosai idan aka kwatanta da yadda hada-hadar kasuwancin take a duniyar intanet. Akwai dalilan da suka sa aka fi samun su a duniyar intanet kamar haka:

- A. Domin takaita kashe kudi ga kamfanoni¹³
- B. Domin nisan kwararru a fannonin da ake bukata¹⁴

Duk wadannan nau'ukan firilancin din kan intanet da aka zayyano a sama, a yau akwai Hausawa da suka rungume su.¹⁵ Kin karawa ma, har an samu ma'aikatu da kamfanonin Hausawa wadanda ke gudanar da ire-iren ayyukan nan na firilancin. Daga cikinsu akwai *Amsoshi Language Serices* (<https://www.amsoshilanguageservices.com>)¹⁶ da *Shawsec* (<https://shawsec.com>)¹⁷ da *3logy* (<https://3logy.com.ng>)¹⁸.

Duk wanda aka dauka daga cikin nau'ukan kasuwanci da ke sama na samar da kudin shiga sosai (duk da ya dogara ga alkaluma daban-daban kamar su lokaci da yanayi da kwarewa da sauransu).¹⁹ Nicol, (2022 p. 1) ta kawo cewa, kudin hada-hadar kasuwar duniyar fassara kadai ya haura dalan Amurka miliyan arba'in (\$40,000,000). Yana da wuya a fitar da kididdigar kason da Hausawa suka dauka daga cikin alkaluman.

3.1.2 Baje haja/koli

A kullum Hausawa na fara rungumar intanet a matsayin kasuwar baje hajojin da suke sayarwa. Wannan na daga misalan harkallolin da ake gudanarwa a duniyoyi guda biyu (na zahiri da na badini). Tun a shekarar 2021, Oyekanmi, (2021 p. 1) ya bayyana cewa

¹³ Idan kamfani na aiki da ma'aikatan firilancin, to ya huta biyan su albashi kowace wata. A maimakon haka, zai riƙa biyan su ne kawai yayin da ya ba su aiki.

¹⁴ Misali, kamfanonin fassara da ke nahiyoyin da ke nesa da kasar Hausa, ya fi musu sauƙi su riƙa aiki da ma'aikatan firilancin don yi musu fassarori ta kan intanet a maimakon zuwa kasar Hausa domin samun mai fassara ko kuma bukatar mai fassarar ya je can domin samun su.

¹⁵ An tabbatar da wannan bayani ta hanyar tattaunawa da waɗansu Hausawa gogaggu a harkar firilancin, da kuma bincikawa a waɗansu manyan kafafen baje kolin firilancin na intanet da suka haɗa da Fiverr (<https://www.fiverr.com>) da LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com>) da ProZ (<https://www.proz.com>) da Upwork (<https://www.upwork.com>).

¹⁶ Sun shahara a fannin firilancin da ya shafi kimiyyar harshe da bincike (M.U. Arabi, kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 5 ga watan Maris, 2023).

¹⁷ Sun shahara a fannin firilancin da ya shafi tsaron kafafen intanet da na'urori (S. Auwal, kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 5 ga watan Maris, 2023).

¹⁸ Sun shahara a fannin koyar da ilimummukan zamani kamar na'urori, intanet, sakago da sauransu.

¹⁹ A bisa dalilai na sirrantawa, wannan bincike ba zai iya kawo misalan kididdigar kuɗaɗen da waɗansu Hausawa masu harkan firilancin ke samu ba. Amma binciken ya ci karo da Hausawan da suke iya aikin har sama da miliyan biyar (#5,000,000) a cikin wata guda.

rahoton *National Bureau of Statistics* (Hukumar Kididdiga ta Kasa) ta nuna cewa kashi 22% na masu kananan kasuwanci ne ke amfani da intanet wajen gudanar da kasuwancinsu.

Hausawa masu kanana da manyan kasuwanci da dama na amfani da kafafen intanet daban-daban domin tallata kasuwancinsu. Waɗansu na amfani da kafafen sada zumunta (WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, da sauransu),²⁰ waɗansu kuwa na buɗe kafafensu na kansu ko su haɗa guiwa da waɗansu masu kafafen intanet domin sama musu gurabu. A duba misalai a hotunan da ke kasa:

Hoto na 1: Tallan hajoji a kan sitatus ɗin WhatsApp

Tushe: An ɗauko su daga sitatus ɗin waɗansu Hausawa a WhatsApp.

Hoto na 1 da ke sama na ɗauke da haɗakar hotuna 4 da aka ɗauko daga sitatus ɗin WhatsApp na mutane daban-daban. 3 na farko mata ne da ke sayar da kayan kwalliya (hoto na 1), takalma da jakukkuna (hoto na 2), da kuma turamen zannuwa (hoto na 3). Hoto na ƙarshen kuma an ɗauko daga sitatus ɗin namiji da ke sayar da shaddodi da yaduna. Duk waɗannan kasuwanci ne kanana.

²⁰ Da wuya mutum ya karade sitatus ɗinsa na WhatsApp ba tare da cin karo da hajojin da waɗansu ke tallatawa ba, irin su tufafi, turare, na'urori, da sauransu.

Hoto na 2: Shafin sayar da littattafan Hausa da ke kan kafar intanet ta WikiHausa.

Madogara: Daga <https://wikihaus.com.ng/product-category/hausa-novels/>.

Sabanin hoto na 1, hoto na 2 misali ne na kafar intanet ta Hausawa da ke ba da dama ga waɗansu ‘yan kasuwa daban su baje hajojinsu. Yayin da aka yi ciniki, masu kafar za su dauki wani kaso daga ribar a matsayin ladan aikinsu.

Hoto na 3: Kasuwancin katin waya da data da katin lantarki (da sauransu) a kan intanet

Madogara: Kafar intanet ta Malam Ahmad Ali Galadima (<https://sahabdata.com.ng>)

Hoto na 3 da ke sama an dauki shi ne daga kafar kasuwancin kan intanet ta *Sahab Data*. Wannan nau'in kasuwanci ne na kan intanet mallakin Bahausha. Malam Ahmad Ali Galadima haifaffen jahar Kano ne wanda yanzu ke gudanar da kasuwancinsa a jahar

Bauchi. A da dole sai mutum ya je ofishi ko shago ko ya kira waya kafin a saka masa katin waya ko datar burawuzin ko katin talabijin ko na wutar lantarki da sauransu. Da fikira irin ta Malam Ahmad, yanzu mutum zai iya hawa kafar intanet din kasuwancin masu irin wannan kasuwanci ya sayi duk abin da yake bukatar saya da kansa ba tare da sai ya yi magana da wani ba.

3.1.3 Dillanci

Manyan kamfanonin kasuwancin duniya da dama na da tsarin dillancin kan intanet. Wannan binciken ya gano cewa Hausawa masu yawa na cin gajiyyar wannan tsari. Yana da sigogi daban-daban sannan ana iya samun bambancin sunaye da kamfanoni mabambanta suka yi masa. Duk da haka, a gama-gari an fi kiransa *affiliate marketing*, wanda a fassarar kai tsaye zai kasance “kasuwancin dosane,” amma a hakikanin yadda lamuran ke gudana, “dillanci” ne kai tsaye.

Kamfanoni da suka hada da masu sayar da littattafai, na’urori, ababen hawa, tufafi, abinci, mayuka, da sauransu, duk suna ba da damar dillanci. Dillali zai tallata kayan kamfani. Idan aka saya ta dalilin tallar da ya yi, to yana da kaso cikin ribar, wato dai la’ada (royalty). Akwai manyan nau’ukan dillancin kan intanet guda uku kamar haka:

- i. Budɛ reshen kasuwanci
- ii. Dora likau da samfuran hajoji a kan kafar intanet din dillali
- iii. Yada likau da samfuran hajoji a kafafen sada zumunta

Hoto na 4: Dillanci ta hanyar dora likau a kan kafar intanet

Madogara: An dauko daga kafar Amsoshi (www.amsoshi.com).

A hoto na 4 da ke sama, za a ga misalin yadda aka dora likau da ke boye cikin hoto a kan kafar intanet da ta kasance ta Hausawa. Yayin da masu ziyarar wannan kafa suka bi likau din zuwa kafar masu kamfanin har suka yi huldoyyar kasuwanci, to masu wannan kafa za su samu kamasho.

Hoto na 5: Dillanci a kan kafar Paxful.

Madogara: An dawko daga <https://paxful.com/ha/buy-bitcoin-kiosk>.

Paxful babbar kafa ce ta hada-hadar kasuwancin kuɗin intanet. Ita ma na da tsarin dillanci. A hoto na 5 da ke sama, an ga yadda Paxful ke ba da damar a buɗe abin da ta kira “shago” a kan kafarta. Wato zai zama tamkar wani karamin shago da mai shi zai rika samun kayayyakin da zai rika dillanci daga asalin babban kantin Paxful.²¹

Dangane da tura likau ta kafafen sada zumunta kuwa, Hausawa da yawa sun samu kuɗaɗe daga dillancin *PalmPay* da *Kuda* da *Manhajar Abeg* da *Chipper Cash* da makamantansu.²²

3.1.4 Kasuwancin kuɗin intanet

Kuɗin intanet (crypto currency) nau’i ne na kuɗin baɗini da ke wanzuwa a duniyar intanet. Buhari,³ (2021 p. 1) ya bayyana shi a matsayin “kuɗi da ake amfani da su a cikin kwamfuta wanda za a iya saye da saidawa da su a cikin hanya mai sauki.” Wani abin burgewa shi ne, ana iya sayen kuɗin intanet ta amfani da kuɗin zahiri, ana kuma iya

²¹ Fassara illahirin shafin zuwa Hausa na kara nuni da yadda Hausawa ke cikin wannan harkar dillanci.

²² A. Sani (Kebantacciyar Tattaunawa, Maris 6, 2023).

sayen su ta amfani da wani nau'in kuɗin intanet na daban. Kididigar Tripple A (2023 p. 1) ya nuna cewa, ya zuwa 2022, kashi 10.34% na 'yan Nijeriya sun mallaki kuɗin intanet.

Batey, (n.d.) ta tabbatar da cewa, kuɗin intanet na farko shi ne Bitcoin wanda aka samar tun a shekarar 2008 sannan aka fara amfani da shi a shekarar 2009.²³ Ya zuwa yau akwai nau'ukan kuɗaɗen intanet daban-daban waɗanda kuma kullum ke kara yawa saboda sababbi da ake samarwa. Pi na ɗaya daga cikin waɗanda suka fi kaurin suna tsakanin Hausawa, inda har aka samu waƙoƙi²⁴ da maganganun malamai da masana daban-daban game da shi. Bayan haka, har fim sukutum aka yi game da Pi, mai suna *'Yan Pi Network*.

Akwai manyan nau'uka ko hanyoyin kasuwancin kuɗin intanet guda biyu da wannan bincike ya ci karo da Hausawa da dama na gudanarwa. Na farkonsu shi ne *trading* wanda a nan aka fassara shi a matsayin *cinikayya*. Na biyun kuwa shi ne *holding*, wanda aka fassara shi da *rikewa*.

Cinikayya shi ne tsarin da ake saye da sayar da kuɗin intanet nan take domin samun karamar riba. Wannan na buƙatar lissafi da kyakkyawan hasashe. M.M. Manga, (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 7 ga watan Fabarairu 2023) ya bayyana yadda ake wannan cinikayya. Mutum zai sayi wani nau'in kuɗin intanet bayan yin lissafin cewa darajarsa za ta karu bayan 'yan kwanaki kaɗan, domin ya sayar ya samu riba. Haka kuma, mutum na iya saye a wurin ɗan kasuwa mai sauƙin farashi, sannan ya sayar wa ɗan kasuwa mai farashin da ya fi inda ya saye domin samun riba.

Rikewa shi ne tsarin da mutum zai sayi kuɗin intanet sannan ya ajiye shi na tsawon lokaci. Ana yin haka ne domin bin babbar riba. Akan saye a lokacin da ake kira *red market* (jar kasuwa – wato lokacin da darajar kuɗaɗen intanet ta faɗi) sannan a sayar a lokacin da ake kira *green market* (koriyar kasuwa – wato lokacin da darajar kuɗaɗen intanet ta tashi).

²³ Wanda ya samar da Bitcoin ya bayyana sunansa a matsayin Satoshi Nakamoto. Sai dai har yanzu ba a san mai wannan sunan ba. Ba a ma san mutum guda ne ko ƙungiya ce ba. Domin samun ƙarin bayani, a duba, Batey, (n.d.).

²⁴ <https://www.amsoshi.com/2021/12/yan-pi-network.html>

Daga cikin manyan kafofin hada-hadar kuɗaɗen intanet akwai:

Binance - <https://www.binance.com/>

Gate - <https://www.gate.io/>

Crypto - <https://crypto.com/>

OKX - <https://www.okx.com/>

KUCCOIN - <https://www.kucoin.com/>

Paxful - <https://www.paxful.com>

An samu Hausawa da dama da ke bayani game da lamuran da suka shafi kasuwancin kuɗin intanet. Yawanci sukan yi ne a tashoshin kan intanet masu zaman kansu. Daga cikinsu akwai Mujahid Muhammad Manga da ke da kafar TikTok mai suna *Abumaher*. Shi kuwa Sunusi Danjuma Ali tasha yake da ita a kan YouTube mai suna *SunusiCryptoTV*.

3.1.5 Talla (Advertisement)

A wannan bagiren talla na nufin tallata haja ko ra'ayi ko akidar wani ko waɗansu domin samun kuɗi. Kusan wannan nau'in talla ba a samun sa a duniyar zahiri - duk da akan samu makamantansa da ake gudanarwa a gidajen talabijin da na rediyo da kuma cikin finafinai. A yau Hausawa da dama sun yi nisa a wannan harkar kasuwanci. Ana gudanar da tallar kan intanet ta fuskoki daban-daban da suka haɗa da:

A. Talla a kan kafafen intanet (Websites and blogs)

Wanda ke da kafar intanet da ta gawurta, yana da damar ɗora tallace-tallace a kai. Tallar na iya kasancewa ta fuskoki guda biyu, ko dai AdSense²⁵ ko kuma kebantattun tallace-tallace.²⁶

²⁵ Wannan nau'in talla ne inda ake rajista da kamfanin Google. Kamfanin na Google ne zai riƙa karɓar tallace-tallace sannan ya riƙa ɗora waɗanda suka dace a kafar wanda ya yi rajistar (ta la'akari da nau'ukan mutanen da ke ziyartar kafar tasa).

²⁶ Wannan nau'in tallace-tallace ne da ake karɓa daga ɗaiɗaikun mutane ko kamfanoni ko ƙungiyoyi. Kai tsaye akan yi ciniki da yarjejeniyar yadda tallar za ta kasance (kamar abin da ya shafi farashi, da shafukan da za a ɗora su da tsawon lokacin da za su ɗauka kafin a sauke su).

Hoto na 6: Talla a kafar intanet

Madogara: An dāuko daga <https://www.isyaku.com/search/label/FADAKARWA>

A hoto na 6 da ke sama, za a ga yadda aka dōra talla a kafar Isyaku. Mamallakin wannan kafa Bahaushe ne dān jahar Kebbi, mai suna Isyaku Garba.

B. Talla a shafuka da zaurukan kafafen intanet

Wadānda ke da zauruka da shafuka a kafafen intanet na da damar dōra tallace-tallace idan sun cika ka'idojin da ake bukata. Wadānnan ka'idoji sun danganta da kafar da kuma mutum ko mutane ko kamfanonin da za su ba da tallar. Sannan ka'idojin na sauyawa lokaci zuwa lokaci.

Hausawa da dama na samun kuɗi a YouTube da Facebook da Instagram da TikTok a dalilin irin wannan nau'in tallar. Mawaƙan Hausa na zamani da 'yan barkwanci Hausawa da dama ta wannan hanyar suka fi samun kuɗi. Tuni masu tsara finafinan Hausa ma suka rungumi wannan nau'in kasuwanci inda suke sakin finafinansu a kan YouTube tare da dōra tallace-tallace domin samun kuɗin shiga. Fitattun finafinan Hausa masu dogon zango da ake sakewa a kan YouTube sun haɗa da *Labarina* da *Izzar So* da *Amaryar TikTok* da *Asin da Asin* da makamantansu.

Daga cikin 'yan barkwancin Hausa kuwa da suka shahara da kafafen YouTube da TikTok (wadānda ke dōra tallace-tallace kan tashoshi ko shafukansu) akwai Abubakar Sadauki da aka fi sani da *Aibs_Fulani*. Akwai kuma Mu'azu Muhammad da aka fi sani da *Bushkido*. Sannan akwai Ali Muhammad Idris da aka fi sani da *Madagwal*, I.A. Adam (kebantacciyar tattaunawa, 11 ga watan Maris, 2023).

C. Talla ta hanyar raba likau

Wannan nau'in kasuwancin kan intanet ya shafi tura sakonnin talla na wani kamfani a kafafen sada zumunta ta sigar likau.²⁷ Mai wannan kasuwancin na daukar likau da za a rika ba shi a kowace rana (ko wani lokacin da aka kayyade) sannan ya raba a kafafen sada zumunta irin su Facebook, TikTok, WhatsApp, da sauransu.

Hausawa da dama sun samu riba mai yawa daga wannan kasuwanci. Duk da haka wannan nau'in kasuwanci tamkar caca yake. Dalili kuwa shi ne, sau da dama ire-iren waɗannan nau'ukan kasuwanci na yin batar dabo na farat daya. A haka ake rufewa da kudaden waɗanda suka yi aiki ba a biya su ba, da kuma kudaden waɗanda suka sanya hannayen jari.²⁸ Daga cikin ire-irensu da aka ci kasuwarsu kuma suka watse akwai:

- a. Uwork
- b. Insme
- c. MyBonus

3.2 Abubuwan da mai kasuwanci a kan intanet ke bukata

Daga cikin nau'ukan ayyukan kan intanet da aka tattauna a karkashin 3.1.1 zuwa 3.1.5, akwai waɗanda suka kasance gama-gari tsakanin mutanen duniya. Waɗansu daga cikinsu kuwa, ana sa ran su kasance keɓantattu ga Hausawa. Misali, duk aikin firilancin da ya shafi harshe ko al'ada, kai tsaye an fi son ɗan gado ba ɗan haye ba. Ma'ana dai, an fi son wanda Hausa ke matsayin harshen uwa gare shi. Ana hakan ne don gudun abin da Bunza, (2015) ya kira "Grammatical Rift" (p. 5) da "Cultural Lacuna" (p. 11) wato "Gibin Nahawu" da "Gibin Al'ada." Bayan haka, abubuwan da ake bukata na iya bambanta daga kasuwanci zuwa kasuwanci. Duk da haka, akwai waɗanda suka kasance gama-gari kamar haka:

1. Na'ura mai sauri da inganci daidai da nau'in kasuwancin da za a gudanar²⁹

²⁷ A waɗansu lokuta yakan kasance bidiyo ko hoto.

²⁸ An samu waɗannan bayanai daga tattaunawa da aka yi da Hausawa da suka ci wannan kasuwa. A. Sani (keɓantacciyar tattaunawa, 11 ga watan Maris, 2023) ya yi cikakken bayanin yadda harƙallolin ke gudana.

²⁹ Abubuwan da ake dubawa a wannan fannin sun haɗa da saurin na'ura, girman kwakwalwarta, faɗin sikirin dinta, da nau'inta. Akwai nau'ukan ayyukan da kai tsaye kamfani na iya ba da bayanin nau'in

2. Sabis din intanet mai karfi da rashin yankewa
3. Wuri mai sirri da rashin hayaniya³⁰
4. Kwarewa sosai a fannin da aka sa a gaba
5. Tallar haja (kwarewa) a kan intanet³¹
6. Girmama lokaci
7. Gaskiya da rikon amana

3.3 Allah san barka a kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet

Samuwar damarmakin kasuwanci a kan intanet ya zo da alfanu ta fuskoki daban-daban ga Hausa. Daga ciki akwai:

1. **Hutun jiki:** Wadansu daga cikin nau'ukan kasuwanci na da sauƙin gudanarwa. Misali, kasuwancin sayar da data da katin waya da na wutar lantarki da talabijin duk saita su kawai ake yi a bar su a kan intanet. Dan kasuwa ba ya buƙatar wata wahalar ciniki ko mifa kaya. A maimakon haka, kwastomomi su ne za su biya kuɗi kawai su dauki kaya. Yana kwance sai dai ya ji shigar kuɗi a akawun dinsa.³²
2. **Karancin jin rauni sakamakon aiki:** Sabanin ayyukan bayyane da dama da ana iya samun rauni ta dalilinsu (daga kayan aiki, ko faɗuwa, ko haɗari a hanyar zuwa wurin aiki da sauransu), mai aikin kan intanet na da karancin fargabar samun wani rauni sakamakon aikin.³³

na'urar da za a yi amfani da ita domin gudanarwa. Misali, daga shekarar 2020 har zuwa 2023 Hausawa da dama sun yi aiki da kamfanin Appen. Aikin na buƙatar tattara bayanai ne ta amfani da wayar salulula. Haka kuma, duk wanda ya gwada buɗe manhajar XTM a kan waya domin gudanar da fassara, zai ga jan rubutu na masa gargadin cewa dole sai ya yi amfani da kwamfuta.

³⁰ Mafi yawan ayyukan kan intanet na buƙatar sirri. Sau da dama akan buƙaci mutum ya cike abin da aka fi sani da *NDA (Non-Disclosure Agreement)* wato Yarjejeniyar Rife Sirri kafin kulla harƙallar kasuwanci da kamfani a kan intanet.

³¹ Akwai fitattun kafafen intent da suka shahara a wannan fannin. Masu firilancin na zuwa waɗannan kafafe su baje kolin fikirarsu. Kamfanoni daban-daban a faɗin duniya na ziyartar waɗannan kafafe domin duba hajar da ta musu. Nguyen (n.d. p. 1) ya zayyano waɗansu daga cikin fitattun kafafen kamar haka: LinkedIn da freelancer.com da Toptal da Guru da PeoplePerHour da FlexJobs da 99Designs da Fiverr da Upwork da Freelance Writing Gigs.

³² Duk da haka akwai abubuwan da ake buƙata daga gare shi kamar su fara kuɗi a lalitoci da duba daidaiton lamura da kuma sauraren koken kwastomomi.

³³ Duk da haka akan iya samun rauni lokaci zuwa lokaci musamman idan ba a bi fa'idojin aiki ba. Misali, ana iya samun ciwon baya ko ciwon wuya sakamakon daɗewa ana zaune ko zama yadda bai kamata ba, da dai sauransu.

3. **Cikakken 'Yanci:** Koma bayan ayyukan duniyar zahiri, mai aikin firilancin na da 'yanci kan lokacinsa. Yana da zaɓi kan ya karɓi aiki ko kada ya karɓa. Yana da damar tsara lokacinsa yadda yake so sannan ya karɓi ayyuka lokacin da ba shi da waɗansu hidimomin rayuwa a gabansa kawai.
4. **Jari:** Akwai nau'ukan kasuwancin kan intanet da ke bukatar karamin jari kawai. Waɗansu kuwa ba sa ma bukatar jarin. Misali, a firilancin da ya shafi yada likau, ba a bukatar wani jari. Game da abin da ya shafi fassara kuwa, ɗan jarin bai wuce na sayen waya ko kwamfuta ba, sai kuma 'yar datar burawuzin da za a rika sakawa.

Sauran alfanu na gama-gari sun haɗa da:

- a. Rage cunkoso a kan tituna
- b. Rage fitar da sinadaren ababan hawa masu cutar da muhalli

3.4 Kalubale a kasuwancin Hausawa a duniyar intanet

Duk da ɗimbin alfanun da ke tattare da kasuwancin kan intanet, akwai kalubale ko nakasu da ke tattare da shi. A fasa an kawo waɗansu daga ciki.

1. **Rashin ingantaccen sabis:** Har yanzu babu ingantaccen sabis a kasar Hausa. Ko wuraren da ke da sabis mai karfin 4G, a waɗansu lokuta akan samu matsaloli.³⁴ Wannan babban nakasu ne a harkar kasuwancin kan intanet kasancewar akwai lamuran da ke da kayyadden lokacin kammalawa. Sannan akwai kamfanoni da ke bukatar rahoton karfin intanet ɗin mutum kafin fara harkalla da shi.
2. **Matsalar wutar lantarki:** Har ya zuwa lokacin kammala rubuta wannan takarda (Maris 2023) babu ingantacciyar wutar lantarki a kasar Hausa. Hakan kuwa kalubale ne ga nau'ukan kasuwancin kan intanet.
3. **Talauci da karancin tallafi:** Da dama daga cikin nau'ukan kasuwancin kan intanet na bukatar jari. Wannan ya shafi sayen kayan aiki da datar intanet da waɗansu manhajoji

³⁴ Game da wannan, binciken ya kasance ganau a yankunan Kano da Katsina da Sakkwato da Zamfara da Zariya.

da dai makamantansu (wanda ya danganta ga nau'in sana'ar). Hausawa na fuskantar kalubale a wannan bangare sakamakon talauci da karanci ko rashin tallafi.

4. Rashin koyar da zamanantattun darrusa: Zamani ya fara tsere wa tsarin karatun Nijeriya a matakin kasa bai daya, da kuma kasar Hausa a keɓance. Misali, wanda ya karanci harshe na da babban gurbi sosai a kasuwancin intanet, domin zai iya shiga a dama da shi a dukkannin nau'ukan kasuwanci da aka tattauna a farkashin 3.1.1 zuwa 3.1.5 da ke sama. Duk da haka, waɗanda suka karanci Hausa da dama na kasancewa ba tare da aikin yi ba saboda rashin gogewa ta fuskar ire-iren waɗannan nau'ukan kasuwanci.

5. Illata muhalli da yanayi: Daga cikin harkoki da hada-hadar kasuwancin intanet akwai waɗanda ke cutar da muhalli. Misali, haƙon kuɗaɗen intanet irin su Bitcoin na illata muhalli matuƙa. Rahoton Osborne, (2022 p. 1) ya nuna cewa, illar da haƙon Bitcoin ke yi wa muhalli na iya kai wanda man fetur ke yi ta fuskar fitar da sinadarin kabon.

6. Cutar da lafiya: Duk da babu wani bincike da ya tabbatar da cewa yawan kallon sikirin na haifar da dauwamammen ciwon ido, masanan ido irin su Dakta Colman Kraff sun tabbatar da cewa zai iya haifar da matsalolin da suka haɗa da kallo dishi-dishi da ciwon kai har ma da ciwon wuya idan abin ya yi tsanani.³⁵ Abiola, (2021 p. 1) ya tabbatar da cewa radiyeshin da ke fita daga jikin kwamfuta na haifar da illoli da dama, ciki har da hana haihuwa ga maza.

4.0 Sakamakon bincike

Lamarin kasuwanci ya yi daidai da ikirarin ra'in Pulatoriyya, domin kuwa akwai kasuwancin da ke gudana a duniyar zahiri, akwa kuma waɗanda ke gudana a duniyar intanet. Duniyar zahiri na kan tarewa zuwa nau'in kasuwancin duniyar intanet. Hausawa ma da dama sun bi saɗun wannan cigaba.

³⁵ Domin karin bayani, a duba Kraff, (2022 p. 1).

Kasuwancin kan intanet ya rabu zuwa nau'uka daban-daban kamar yadda aka tattauna a farkashin sashe na 3.1 da ke sama. Binciken ya gano cewa ana damawa da Hausawa cikin dukkannin waɗannan kasuwanci. Waɗanda suka karanci harshen Hausa sun fi samun rawar takawa a abin da ya shafi firilancin da ke da alaƙa da harshe (ciki har da fassara da tafintanci da sauransu da aka kawo farkashin 3.1.1).

Waɗannan kasuwancin kan intanet na da dimbin alfanu ga al'ummar Hausa tun daga kan samar da aikin yi har zuwa nisantar haɗurra, da dai sauransu da aka zayyano a farkashin 3.3 da ke sama. A ɓangare guda kuwa, duk da dimbin alfanun da kasuwancin kan intanet ya zo wa Hausawa da shi, yana tattare da kalubale kamar yadda aka gani ga farkashin 3.4 da ke sama.

Dangane da waɗannan kalubale, Hausawa 'yan kasuwan kan intanet na iya riko da dabarar amfani da hanyoyin samun sabis ɗin intanet sama da guda. Wannan zai ba su damar kauce wa shiga halin kaƙanikayi sakamakon gushewar ƙarfin sabis ko sabis ɗin kacokan a lokacin aiki. Sannan kada su bari a bar su a baya wajen rungumar sababbin sabis ɗin intanet na zamani masu ƙarfi, musamman yanzu da ake sauraron ƙarasowar sabis ɗin 5G da na *Starlink*.

Game da wutar lantarki kuwa, ya kamata gwamnati ta ninka fokarinta na tabbatar da samuwar ingancin wutar lantarki musamman domin samun cigaba mai ɗorewa. Yayin da gwamnati ke fokarin wannan, 'yan kasuwan kan intanet na iya amfani da dabarun da suka haɗa da wutar sola da rumbun cajin kwamfuta (computer power bank) da sauran hanyoyin da ba sa illata muhalli da yanayi.

Ya kamata a mayar da hankali wajen koyar da abubuwan da suka shafi kasuwancin kan intanet musamman a matakin manyan makarantu. Hakan zai ba da damar samun ƙarin aikin yi tare da rage zaman banza. Da taimakon wannan, Hausawa da yawa musamman waɗanda suka karanci harshen Hausa na iya samun hanyar dogaro da kai a saukaƙe.

Dangane da illolin lamuran kasuwancin intanet a kan muhalli da yanayi, akwai buƙatar gwamnatoci da hukumomi da ɗaiɗaikun mutane su yi huɓɓasa wajen ganin an samu

mafi mafi dacewa. Wannan ya hada da fito da dokoki da fa'idoji da suka dace daga bangaren gwamnati, bincike da fadakarwa daga bangaren hukumomi, da kuma bin kyawawan mata kai da ke da akwai daga bangaren daidai kun mutane.

4.1 Kammalawa

Nau'ukan kasuwancin kan intanet na da matuƙar yawa. Da wuya a iya nuna wani abu a kan intanet da ba za a iya kasuwanci da shi ba. Sannu a hankali 'yan kasuwan duniyar zahiri na zamanantar da kasuwancinsu ta hanyar mayar da ita ko wani ɓangare nata zuwa duniyar intanet. A yanzu haka duk manyan kasuwancin duniya sun yi gurbi sosai a kan intanet. Da yiwuwar a shekaru masu zuwa duniyar intanet na iya kwace ta zahiri a fuskar kasuwanci, inda za a samu mafi rinjayen kasuwanci na gudana ne a duniyar intanet sabanin ta zahiri.

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